

Transfer of deoxynivalenol and fumonisins B₁ and B₂ from maize flour to maize/wheat-based bread

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ABSTRACT

Deoxynivalenol (DON) and fumonisins B-type (FBs), mycotoxins synthesized by *Fusarium* spp., cause serious health problems after their intake. These compounds are frequently found in maize and wheat, the most consumed cereals worldwide and main hosts of *Fusarium*, making them a food safety problem. This work studies the effect of the maize/wheat-based breadmaking process on the concentrations of DON and FBs. Breads were made using contaminated maize flour (40 %) mixed with uncontaminated wheat flour (60 %). Three factors were analyzed: mycotoxin contamination level (DON: 1.20 or 0.8 mg/kg; FBs: 1.28 or 0.61 mg/kg), sourdough use (absence, artisan or commercial) and fermentation time (2 or 12 h). Doughs were baked at 200 °C for 40 min. DON and FBs were determined by HPLC-DAD and HPLC-FLD, respectively. Additionally, sourdough microbiota was identified. The only isolated yeast was *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, while lactic acid bacteria showed great variability, being *Lactobacillus plantarum* the most common. FBs concentration remained stable during fermentation; while for DON, the highest change was observed in the loaves with an initial concentration of 1.20 mg/kg, commercial sourdough use and 12 h fermented, showing a 28 % increase in its concentration. After baking, mycotoxin reduction was observed under all conditions, except in the aforementioned one that still showed a 16 % of DON increase. Results indicate that the reduction of DON during breadmaking may not be enough to ensure food safety from borderline contaminated flour to meet legal limits. However, bread with FBs levels below the maximum limits can be produced, even when using contaminated flour.

1. Introduction

Fusarium is a mycotoxigenic fungal genus. Mycotoxins result from secondary metabolism that occurs during the growth of the mould on the infected plant or grains, mainly cereals, at any point during their pre- and post-harvest stages (Drejer Storm et al., 2014; Greeff-Laubscher et al., 2020). This genus is known for its capability to produce a wide range of mycotoxins, such as fumonisins (FUMs), zearalenone (ZEN) or trichothecenes, like deoxynivalenol (DON) or T-2 and HT-2 toxins (Podgórska-Kryszczuk et al., 2022). Due to their bioaccumulation in the organisms, even at low concentrations, all of them are responsible of causing several short and long-term negative effects in humans and animals, including nausea, hepatotoxicity, or carcinogenesis (Ekwoadu et al., 2021; Escrivá et al., 2017).

>50 % of the production of cereal crops in the world are wheat (30 %) and maize (27 %) which are sown worldwide (Erenstein et al., 2021). They are the basis of most of the diets in many regions and cultures,

representing 30–80 % of the daily intake of calories (Iqbal et al., 2020). However, these cereals are the main hosts of *Fusarium* spp. making them and their derived food products the main source of exposure to mycotoxins by the population.

Fusarium verticillioides and *Fusarium proliferatum* are the major pathogens of maize and the main producers of FUMs, where fumonisins B-type (FBs) are the most common type of mycotoxin in this cereal, being fumonisin B₁ (FB₁) the 70 % of all FBs (Fanelli et al., 2013). Recent studies indicate that *F. proliferatum* can infect wheat producing fumonisin B₂ (FB₂) at higher levels than FB₁ (Cendoya et al., 2018). On the other hand, *Fusarium graminearum* and *Fusarium culmorum* are pathogenic either for wheat or maize and widely extended in these crops. Once the plant is infected, they synthesize trichothecene B group mycotoxins. DON, classified in this group, has the highest occurrence in cereal products (Jajić et al., 2008; Lombaert, 2002).

Bread is one of the most important cereal-derived products worldwide. During bread making different physical, chemical and biological

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processes occur that may affect the mycotoxins. If sourdough is used, fermentation involves yeasts and lactic acid bacteria (LAB), which, via enzymatic action, lead to an acidification of the matrix (Schaarschmidt and Fahl-Hassek, 2018). Over the years, the use of sourdough in breadmaking has increased, not only to enhance the organoleptic properties of the bread, but also due to the antifungal properties of the LAB species present in it (Lafuente, 2024; Quattrini et al., 2019). While food companies have standardized LAB species of their commercialized sourdoughs, artisanal ones can present wide variety of LAB which could interact differently with the toxins of the matrix.

Data published about fermentation effect on DON in wheat bread are contradictory; while some authors indicate that fermentation leads to an increase in DON concentration (Bergamini and Catellani, 2010; Lancova et al., 2008; Zhang and Wang, 2015), others suggest a reduction during the fermentation step (Podgórska-Kryszczuk et al., 2022; Samar et al., 2001; Schaarschmidt and Fahl-Hassek, 2018). Meanwhile, there are no studies carried out on maize as a matrix together with sourdough. On the other hand, literature on FBs shows more consistent results finding different levels of reduction in both maize and wheat fermented dough (Dawlal et al., 2017; de Melo Nazareth et al., 2019; Mokoena et al., 2005; Niderkorn et al., 2006).

Baking is another major step in breadmaking. In general, mycotoxins are very thermostable at temperature levels from 80 to 121 °C (Kabak, 2009). Studies published also show contradictory results on baking effect on mycotoxins. While some authors reported high reduction rates (Numanoglu et al., 2012; Pacin et al., 2010; Vidal et al., 2014a), others report low degradation or no effect (Numanoglu et al., 2010; Stadler et al., 2019), and others described an increase of DON after the baking process (de Angelis et al., 2013; Zhang and Wang, 2015). FBs are less thermoresistant than DON, and published data show a trend of degradation at different rates when FBs are exposed to baking temperatures (Bryla et al., 2017; El-Sayed et al., 2003; Meca et al., 2010).

There is a lack of data on the fate of mycotoxins throughout the entire breadmaking process, including fermentation with sourdough microbiota and baking, in maize-mixed cereal-based products. The aim of this study was to determine the effect of the breadmaking process under different fermentation and sourdough conditions and baking on DON and FBs concentrations during the production of bread using a complex matrix (maize and wheat).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals and reagents

HPLC grade methanol and acetonitrile (≥ 99.98 % purity) were acquired from Thermo Fisher Scientific (Massachusetts, USA). Ultra purified water was supplied by a Milli-Q SP equipment (Millipore Corp., Brussels, Belgium). Acetic acid 0.1 % was made by adding 1 mL of glacial acetic acid from VWR Chemicals (Llinars del Vallés, Spain) in 999 mL of ultra purified water. PBS solution was made by dissolving 0.2 g of potassium chloride, 0.2 g of potassium dihydrogen phosphate, 1.16 g of disodium phosphate anhydrous, and 8.0 g of sodium chloride in 1 L of pure water. Its pH was adjusted to 7.4 by adding 1 M hydrochloric acid. All products were obtained from Panreac (Castellar del Vallès, Spain), except sodium chloride (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Massachusetts, USA). Mycotoxin standards used were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Missouri, USA). Immunoaffinity chromatography columns (IAC) for DON (DONPREP®) and FBs (FUMONIPREP®) extracts clean-up were purchased from R-Biopharm (Darmstadt, Germany). OPA reagent was made by dissolving 40 µg of O-phthalaldehyde from Sigma Aldrich (Missouri, USA) in 1 mL of methanol, 10 mL of sodium tetraborate from Sigma Aldrich (Missouri, USA) and 50 µL of mercaptoethanol molecular biology grade from Scharlab (Barcelona, Spain).

2.2. Flour obtention and contamination

Commercial maize flour was obtained from Farinera La Segarra S.A. (Maldà, Spain) and commercial strong wheat flour from Harinera La Meta S.A. (Lleida, Spain).

To obtain contaminated maize flour, two different strains of *Fusarium* were used: *F. graminearum* (F.45) to produce DON and *F. verticillioides* (F.109) to produce FBs. Both strains are maintained in the strain collection of the Department of Food Technology, Engineering and Science at the University of Lleida (Spain). These strains were incubated for 7 days at 25 °C in Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) medium. Once the incubation was completed, they were inoculated separately in Petri dishes containing 20 g of maize flour and later 1 mL of distilled water, both previously sterilized at 121 °C for 15 min. Petri dishes were placed for 20 days at 30 °C in different airtight containers, in groups of 12, with 2 flasks of 200 mL of sterile water to ensure an atmosphere with high relative humidity. After the incubation period, the flour was dried in a UF 160TS Memmert oven dryer (Memmert GmbH + Co. Kg, Schwabach, Germany) at 40 °C for 48 h, and thoroughly homogenized. At the end of the process, two different flours were obtained: 2 kg of flour A contaminated with DON by *F. graminearum* and 2 kg of flour B contaminated with FBs by *F. verticillioides*.

To conduct the experiment, two batches of flour were prepared: one with a final concentration of 1.20 mg/kg of DON and 1.00 mg/kg of FB₁, and the other with a final concentration of 0.80 mg/kg of DON and 0.50 mg/kg of FB₁. For this, commercial and contaminated flours (A and B) were mixed in different proportions to achieve the previously mentioned concentrations. Afterwards, it was confirmed by HPLC that the prepared flours had the expected concentration. The combined FB₁ + FB₂ contaminations were 1.28 mg/kg (high-contaminated flour) and 0.61 mg/kg (low-contaminated flour).

2.3. Sourdough obtention and analysis

Two different sourdoughs were used in this experiment. One was *Sapore Matrum* purchased from Puratos S.A. (Girona, Spain) and the other was artisan homemade and refreshed in the laboratory by mixing water and commercial wheat flour (50: 50 v/v) and leaving it to ferment at room temperature every 24 h.

2.3.1. Physicochemical analysis

The following pH, titratable acidity (TTA) and water activity (a_w) tests were performed according to Paramithiotis et al. (2010):

To determine the pH value, 10 g of each sourdough were sampled and homogenized with 90 mL of distilled water by a Seward Stomacher 400 Circulator (Seward Ltd., London, UK) and then measured by a Basic 20 pH-meter (Crison Instruments S.A., Alella, Barcelona).

To determine the TTA, the same sampling methodology was carried out and each sample was alkalified by adding 0.1 M NaOH to a final pH value of 8.5.

The a_w of each sourdough was measured with an AquaLab 3TE (Decagon Devices, Washington, USA).

2.3.2. Microbiological analysis

Sourdough samples were prepared by blending 10 g of each sample with 90 mL of 0.9 % NaCl by using the Stomacher. To determine the number of colony forming units (CFU) serial dilutions for each sample were performed. Then, 0.1 mL of each diluted sample was plated in YGC medium (Biokar diagnostics, Allone, France) and MRS medium (Biokar diagnostics, Allone, France) supplemented with 2 % (w/v) maltose to subsequently calculate the CFU for yeast and LAB, respectively. All plates were incubated at 25 °C inside anaerobic jars for 48 h. Anaerobic conditions were established using GasPak™ EZ Anaerobe Container System Sachets (Becton, Dickson and Company, Franklin Lakes, USA), which reduce O₂ and generate CO₂. To ensure anaerobic conditions, Microbiology Anaerotest® strips (Merck Millipore, Massachusetts, USA)

were used, which change their color from blue to white in absence of O₂.

To perform microbial identification, several colonies of yeast and LAB were isolated and sub-cultured from the selected plates. Once grown, the isolates were classified by microscope observation based on their morphology characteristics (size and shape). A selected subset of them were identified through molecular methods by sequencing their DNA. DNA extraction was performed by resuspending each selected colony in 100 µL of PrepMan Ultra reactive (Applied Biosystems, Massachusetts, USA) and heating it up to 100 °C for 10 min. DNA was purified through centrifugation at 1200 g for 2 min and, subsequently, 50 µL of supernatant were sampled. To perform the sample amplification, the following primers were selected: both 27F (AGAGTTT-GATCMTGGCTCAG) and 699R (RGGGTTGCGCTCGTT) were used to amplify rRNA 16S gen fragment for LAB samples and both NL1 (GCA-TATCAATAAGCGGAGGAAAAG) and NL4 (GGTCCGTGTTTCAAGGG) used to amplify D1/D1 gen fragment for yeast samples. For each sample, 1 µL was mixed with 20 pmol of its respective primer by DreamTaq DNA polymerase kit (Thermo Fischer Scientific, Massachusetts, USA). Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) amplification process was carried out in ProFlex PCR System thermocycler (Applied Biosystems, Massachusetts, USA). All sample reactions were made in 35 cycles with the following conditions: 30 s at 95 °C for separation, 30 s at 55 °C for hybridization and 1 min at 72 °C for extension (in last cycle extension was of 10 min). PCR products were analyzed through electrophoresis, made by agarose (1 % w/v) in Tris, borate and EDTA (TBE) 1 × buffer (Sigma, Missouri, USA). Amplified fragments were purified with NucleoSpin Gel and PCR

clean-up kit (Machery-Nagel, Düren, Germany) and subsequently sequenced with BigDye Terminator v3.1 Cycle Sequencing kit (Applied Biosystems, Massachusetts, USA) by ABI 3500xl automated capillary sequencer (Applied Biosystems, Massachusetts, USA). Conting was applied to the bacterial sequences by BioEdit program with its biological sequence alignment editor. Finally, all sequences were compared with GenBank National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) database through Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST) program.

2.4. Bread making and experimental setup

A full factorial design was carried out with 3 factors: mycotoxin contamination level (high and low), sourdough use (absence (WSD), artisan (ASD) and commercial (CSD)) and fermentation time (2 and 12 h) (Fig. 1). That means twelve different conditions, which were repeated by triplicated. Sampling was made after kneading, after fermentation and after baking, and all weights recorded along the process.

2.5. Standard preparation

DON, FB₁ and FB₂ standards were resuspended in methanol at concentrations of 872, 250 and 500 µg/mL, respectively, and stored at -18 °C. DON and FB₁ calibration curves were prepared at the following concentrations: 2.00, 1.50, 1.00, 0.75, 0.50, 0.25 and 0.10 µg/mL. FB₂ calibration curve was made to have half of FB₁ concentration. DON stock solution was confirmed according to AOAC Official Methods of Analysis

Fig. 1. Breadmaking process.

-Chapter 49- (AOAC, 2005) by a UV spectrophotometer (UV-1600PC; VWR, Pennsylvania, EEUU) at 219 nm.

2.6. Mycotoxins extraction, clean-up and detection

All samples collected from the bread making process were dried in a Memmert oven dryer at 40 °C for 48 h and stored at 5 °C.

2.6.1. DON

Each sample was grounded and 5 g were taken and blended in 40 mL of purified water by a magnetic stirrer for 15 min. Afterwards, samples were centrifuged at 9000 rpm and 4 °C for 10 min. Subsequently, supernatants were collected by filtering the samples through Whatman glass microfiber (Cytiva, Barcelona, Spain). Eight milliliters of each sample were loaded into a DONPREP® IAC and then washed with 10 mL of purified water. DON was eluted from the IAC by pipetting 1.5 mL of methanol and to ensure the complete recovery of DON this solvent was backflushed 3 times. As a last step, another 1.5 mL of methanol were loaded for a final elution. Afterwards, samples were completely dried through a nitrogen stream at 40 °C.

Before HPLC analysis, the samples were resuspended in 1 mL of mobile phase, vortexed and filtered by using 0.22 µm pore size PTFE filters (Dominique Dutscher SAS, Bernolsheim, France). DON concentration of each sample was determined by a Waters 2695 High-Performance Liquid Chromatography equipment coupled to a 2996 Waters Diode Array Detector (HPLC-DAD), and a Gemini® C18 column –150 × 4.6 mm with 5 µm of particle size and 110 Å of pore size– (Phenomenex, California, USA) as stationary phase set at 40 °C. The mobile phase used was pure water, methanol and acetonitrile (90:5:5 v/v/v), with a flow rate of 1 mL/min. 50 µL of each sample were injected into the system. DON detection was made at 220 nm wavelength.

2.6.2. FBs

Each sample was grounded and 5 g were taken and blended in 25 mL of a solution made by pure water, methanol and acetonitrile (50:25:25 v/v/v) by a magnetic stirrer for 15 min. Then, samples were centrifuged at 9000 rpm and 23 °C for 10 min. Subsequently, supernatants were collected by filtering the samples through Whatman glass microfiber. Afterwards, 10 mL of each sample were diluted in 40 mL of PBS. All 50 mL were loaded into a FUMONIPREP® IAC and washed with 20 mL of PBS. Elution and drying were carried out as for DON.

Samples were resuspended with 1 mL of a solution made with pure water and methanol (50:50 v/v) and were homogenized and filtered as before in the case of DON. FBs concentration of each sample was determined by HPLC with a 2475 Waters Fluorescence Detector (HPLC-FLD) and a Kinetex® PFP column –150 × 4.6 mm with 5 µm of particle size and 100 Å of pore size– (Phenomenex, California, USA) as stationary phase set at 40 °C. The components mobile phases used during analysis were acetonitrile (A), methanol (B) and acetic acid 0.1 % (C), with a flow rate of 1.2 mL/min. This was pumped in gradient mode with linear ramps at different A-B-C rates during time: 0–10 min (15–0–85 %); 10–14 min (5–61–34 %); 14–16 min (5–72–23 %) and 16–20 min (15–0–85 %). Previously to the injection process, 15 µL of each sample were automatically derivatized with 35 µL of OPA reagent and mixed for 0.3 min. FBs detection was made at 335 nm excitation and 440 nm emission wavelengths.

2.7. Method validation and performance

All analytical methods applied to analyse either DON or FBs in maize-wheat based bread were previously validated. To study the accuracy, for each mycotoxin studied, 11 non-contaminated breads were made, and 7 g from each were spiked at three different toxin levels (DON: 0.22, 0.54 and 1.09 mg/kg; FB₁: 0.22, 0.43 and 1.09 mg/kg; FB₂: 0.11, 0.22 and 0.54 mg/kg) and recovery rates were calculated. After the spiking, samples were homogenized by vortexing during 1 min. and

stand for 2 h. Two extra were not spiked and used as blanks. Mycotoxin extraction and analysis were performed as explained in the previous section (2.6 Mycotoxins extraction, clean-up and detection).

The limit of detection (LOD) was assessed as 3 times the signal of noise. The limit of quantification (LOQ) was calculated as 3 times of LOD. Calibration curves for DON and both FBs standards their R² values >0.99.

2.8. Statistics

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to calculate the significance of the analyzed factors and comparison of means was done by using Tukey HSD test at 95 % confidence level (*p* value >0.05). The program used for the statistics was RStudio (version 4.3.0) with R Commander library (version 2.8–0).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Method validation and performance

Results shown in Table 1 indicate that the method used is viable to perform the experiment, as the recovery values are in range of the accepted by the Regulation (EU) 2023/2782 (European Commission, 2023a). This regulation establishes the mycotoxin recovery rates between 70 and 120 %. FB₂ presents one recovery (65.89 %) below the accepted by the legislation; but in our study, we did not meet concentrations higher than 0.3 mg/kg, so this recovery was not used to treat the data.

3.2. Sourdough analysis

3.2.1. Physicochemical analysis

According to Spanish RD 308/2019, which regulates quality standards for bread, a sourdough must meet the following parameters: having a pH value below 4.2 and a TTA above 6 (expressed in consumed mL of 0.1 M NaOH to reach a pH of 8.5). Commercial sourdough showed pH and TTA values of 3.66 and 15, respectively, while the artisan sourdough exhibited values of 3.55 and 19, thus they were suitable values. *a_w* values were 0.989 and 0.996 for the commercial and artisanal sourdoughs, respectively. Artisan sourdough lower pH and higher TTA values may indicate a major proportion of homofermentative LAB than in the commercial sourdough, due to their greater capacity to produce lactic acid (Erkmen and Bozoglu, 2016; Sevgili et al., 2023).

3.2.2. Microbiological analysis

The artisan sourdough showed yeast and LAB populations of 6.6 and 8.8 log CFU/g, respectively, meanwhile the commercial one had populations of 8.0 and 8.5 CFU/g, respectively. LAB population (≥ 8 log CFU/g) in sourdough tends to be higher than yeast population (≤ 7 log CFU/g) by at least one order of magnitude higher, which agrees with the

Table 1
Performance of the analytical methods for DON, FB₁ and FB₂.

	LOD	LOQ	Spiking		Replicates	Recovery
	(mg/kg)	(mg/kg)	Level	(mg/kg)	<i>n</i>	(% ± SD (%))
DON	0.06	0.18	Low	0.22	3	73.40 ± 3.90
			Medium	0.54	5	85.97 ± 1.55
			High	1.09	3	78.00 ± 0.41
FB ₁	0.02	0.06	Low	0.22	3	84.32 ± 12.48
			Medium	0.43	5	97.56 ± 1.70
			High	1.09	3	92.34 ± 0.76
FB ₂	0.06	0.18	Low	0.11	3	76.67 ± 13.91
			Medium	0.22	5	84.84 ± 3.66
			High	0.54	3	65.89 ± 1.21

LOD: Limit of detection; LOQ: Limit of quantification; *n*: number of replicates; SD: Standard deviation.

obtained data (De Vuyst et al., 2014; Minervini et al., 2012).

A total of 21 LAB and 8 yeast colonies were isolated from artisan sourdough, while 13 LAB and 5 yeast colonies were isolated from the commercial one.

Regarding LAB, microbiological composition of the analyzed sourdoughs differed notably from each other (Table 2). The presence of *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* and the abundance found of *Levilactobacillus brevis* confirm the common pattern in artisan sourdoughs (Corsetti and Settanni, 2007; Reale et al., 2011; Ventimiglia et al., 2015). *Pediococcus parvulus*, however, is a very infrequent species in artisan sourdoughs, just found by few authors, such as Comasio et al. (2020) or Martorana et al. (2018), and it is mainly present in fermented drinks (Abrunhosa et al., 2014; Dimopoulou et al., 2021). In commercial sourdough, *Lactobacillus helveticus* was the most abundant despite not being very common; this species is common in rye, and the commercial sourdough was based in wheat and rye (Viard et al., 2016). It should be noted that *Fructilactobacillus sanfranciscensis*, the most extended and key LAB in sourdough fermentations, was not found in either of the analyzed sourdoughs. This scenario allows us to study the interaction of other less common bacteria with DON and FBs mycotoxins during breadmaking.

On the other hand, all identified yeasts from both sourdoughs were *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. Martorana et al. (2018) identified 78 *S. cerevisiae* strains out of the 84 total yeast isolates from sourdough. Indeed, several authors have stated that *S. cerevisiae* is the most predominant over all yeast species found in sourdoughs (Aydin et al., 2022; Boyaci-Gunduz and Erten, 2020; Minervini et al., 2012; Pino et al., 2022). Its dominance among other species is a result of the sourdough physicochemical conditions, being the high acidity and low pH of the matrix combined to the non-competition for carbon and nitrogen nutrient intake against LAB, the main factors of this outcome (Paramithiotis et al., 2010). Indeed *S. cerevisiae* can grow by consuming the lactic acid and the hydrolyzed maltose produced both by the sourdough LAB (Sieuwerts et al., 2018).

3.3. Fate of the mycotoxins during bread making

Two batches of flour were prepared with different mycotoxin concentrations. One with high DON and FBs concentration (1.2 and 1.3 mg/kg, respectively) and other with lower concentration of these mycotoxins (0.8 and 0.6 mg/kg, respectively). After mixing each contaminated flour with the other ingredients, prepared doughs had average concentrations of DON of 0.79 ± 0.09 mg/kg and 0.47 ± 0.01 mg/kg (for high-contaminated and low-contaminated doughs, respectively) and FBs of 1.06 ± 0.07 mg/kg and 0.49 ± 0.1 mg/kg (for high-contaminated and low-contaminated doughs, respectively). For the 12 conditions tested, the mycotoxin concentration in each dough was considered as initial condition.

3.3.1. Fermentation

The mycotoxin variation during fermentation is represented in Fig. 2.

Table 2
Isolated bacterial species from sourdough.

Identification	Type	Sourdough	% ^a	% ^b
<i>Levilactobacillus brevis</i>	Obligate heterofermentative	Artisan	53.84	36.84
<i>Pediococcus parvulus</i>	Obligate homofermentative	Artisan	38.46	26.32
<i>Lactiplantibacillus plantarum</i>	Facultative heterofermentative	Artisan	7.70	10.53
<i>Lactocaseibacillus paracasei</i>	Facultative heterofermentative	Commercial	16.67	5.26
<i>Lactobacillus helveticus</i>	Obligate homofermentative	Commercial	66.66	21.05

^a Percentage of strains for each sourdough.

^b Percentage of strains over the total isolated strains.

In most cases fermentation led to a slight increasing in DON (2 to 28 %) and FBs (2 to 23 %) levels, except one case in DON and two cases in FBs that showed the opposite trend. Anyway, this trend was only significant in 5 cases, mainly for DON, when using CSD.

Valle-Algarra et al. (2009) did not observe significant changes in DON levels in their doughs (only composed of *S. cerevisiae* yeasts) during fermentation. They also observed a slight increasing trend of 2.5 % and 5 % in their 0.2 and 1.5 mg/kg samples spiked DON, respectively, which aligns with our WSD samples (2.5 % for low-contaminated and 6.5 % for high-contaminated doughs). Different DON reduction levels have been reported by applying different time-temperature conditions. Doughs fermented at 30 °C for 45–60 min have not shown any reduction meanwhile doughs fermented at 50 °C for 40–60 min showed reductions from 41 to 56 % (Samar et al., 2001). Higher fermentation temperatures appear to have a huge influence in mycotoxin level reduction by yeasts. Likewise, in the present experiment, no DON reductions were observed in any of WSD samples fermented at room temperature (20 °C approx.) for either 2 or 12 h. It appears that temperature has greater impact than time or initial mycotoxin concentration on the reduction of DON by *S. cerevisiae* during fermentation process.

As shown in Fig. 2, significant DON increases are observed, mainly when CSD was used. The highest change was observed in CSD fermented for 12 h with high initial DON contamination. In this case the initial DON level was 0.67 ± 0.03 mg/kg and ended up to 0.85 ± 0.02 mg/kg, representing a 28 % increase of DON concentration. Zhang and Wang (2015) also reported a significant increase of DON during fermentation, which they attributed to the effect of the released yeast enzymes that hydrolyze DON-3-glucoside (DON-3-Glc) to DON. This could hardly have occurred in our case as flour was contaminated with *F. graminearum*, while DON-3-Glc is a biologically modified DON toxin conjugated by plants during the mould infestation. Therefore, mould inoculation in the flour cannot trigger the reaction to form DON-3-Glc, so this is not a suitable explanation for 28 % increase of DON, and the other significant increases observed. Bergamini and Catellani, 2010, after using sourdough in their recipe, reported a significant increase of DON levels (31 to 46 %) in their samples. They correlated these changes with the possible capability of sourdough bacteria to release the matrix-bound DON by cleaving or solubilizing it during the fermentation process; this could be a suitable explanation in our case. For example, Vidal et al. (2017) focused on the effect of xylanase and α -amylase enzymes during wheat bread making process, concluding that these enzymes led to DON releases during dough fermentation. DON releases occur by the specific hydrolyzation of its bound with the matrix biopolymers (Tan et al., 2024).

Regarding FBs, there was a general trend to increase during fermentation, but it was only significant when CSD was added and fermentation lasted for 12 h. Nyamete et al. (2016) fermented maize porridge at 30 °C for 24 h and observed 14 to 30 % of FB₁ reduction. Dawlal et al. (2017) reported an increase in FBs binding with LAB when the temperature was increased (30 to 37 °C) and when longer fermentation times (1 to 6 days) were applied to the tested maize-based products (ogi and mahewu). The fact that in our study no significant FBs reduction was observed during fermentation may be due to the lower temperature level, lower to that required for LAB to bind FBs. Also, the LAB strains in our sourdough may not have the capacity to bind the toxin, even though some of our identified species, *L. plantarum* and *L. helveticus* have demonstrated this ability (Dawlal et al., 2017; Niderkorn et al., 2006; Nyamete et al., 2016).

3.3.2. Baking

The fate of DON and FBs during baking at 200 °C for 40 min is presented in Fig. 3. In general, FBs showed a higher reduction than DON under the same baking conditions. However, this may not mean that DON is more thermoresistant than FBs. This issue can be a result of the LAB and yeast activity, explained in the previous subsection (3.3.1 Fermentation). The temperature of the dough in the oven rises

Fig. 2. DON and FBs concentration variation during the fermentation step. WSD: Without Sourdough; ASD: Artisan Sourdough; CSD: Commercial Sourdough. Left panel: 2 h fermentation; Right panel: 12 h fermentation. *: Significant difference between the level of toxin after and before fermentation ($p < 0.05$).

Fig. 3. Effect of bread baking (200 °C for 40 min) in DON and FBs levels. WSD: Without Sourdough; ASD: Artisan Sourdough; CSD: Commercial Sourdough. Left panel: 2 h fermentation; Right panel: 12 h fermentation. *: Significant difference between the level of toxin after and before baking ($p < 0.05$).

progressively, which means that there is a period when the temperature of the dough is still optimum for enzyme activity of the present LAB leading to a higher DON release from the matrix by LAB than the

produced in the fermentation at room temperature (Vidal et al., 2017). Moreover, Chlebicz and Śliżewska (2020) performed a study to test the mycotoxin adsorption capability of 12 LAB strains and 6 *S. cerevisiae*

strains at two different temperatures (30 and 37 °C). They observed that FBs were the most adsorbed mycotoxins of all with maximum reduction rates of 77 and 74 % (LAB and yeast, respectively) meanwhile DON was the less adsorbed toxin of them all with maximum reduction rates of 39 and 43 % (LAB and yeast, respectively), after 24 h of incubation. Those reductions are the result of the hydrophobic interactions between the mycotoxins with the cell wall components of LAB and *S. cerevisiae*. Those two phenomena can contribute to the lower DON reduction compared to FBs. To date, no previous studies have been found in relation to the possible release of FBs by the enzymatic activity derived from LAB or temperature effect.

DON levels decreased more when the dough had been fermented for 2 h compared to 12 h. Samples with short fermentation showed reductions ranging from 12.8 to 29.9 %, while long-fermented samples exhibited reductions from 6.2 to 10.8 %. This could be due to the lower microbial population in the short fermentation, while after long fermentation the higher number of LAB and yeast in the first stages of baking could lead to more enzyme activity that ended with more matrix-bound DON release than in the short-fermented samples.

High-contaminated dough fermented for 12 h (CSD) was the only condition that followed, apparently, an opposite path, showing a significant increase of 16 % from the initial DON levels. These results indicate that their population of LAB and yeast during the baking still released matrix-bound DON.

FBs showed higher reductions when the initial toxin concentration was higher (34 to 48 %) than when it was lower (8 to 31 %). The thermal treatment affected differently FB₁ and FB₂ (Table 3), but being FB₁ the most prevalent and abundant of its kind, it is logical that the effect on this toxin impacts the overall fate of FBs. FB₂ does not follow a clear trend according to its initial levels neither seems to affect to the overall FBs levels. For DON, different toxin initial levels did not lead to different reduction levels.

Although after baking reduction in DON and FBs levels were observed, this does not mean that those toxins have been degraded. Mycotoxins are very stable under typical heat treatments, which do not begin to have detoxifying effects until temperatures of 150 °C (Kabak, 2009). In our experiment, although the oven temperature was set to 200 °C, the breadcrumb temperature did not exceed 100 °C. Therefore, we cannot state that the reduction in DON and FBs levels is due to degradation, but rather to chemical modification. FBs are mainly affected by Maillard reaction with sugars, which leads to thermal modifications like *N*-(1-deoxy-D-fructos-1-yl) FB₁ or *N*-(carboxymethyl) FB₁. On the other hand, DON can be thermally transformed to norDON A-F or to 9-hydroxymethyl DON (Rychlik et al., 2014). All these biological and chemically modified forms are usually not analyzed by routine analysis. Their formation leads to a reduction of their free/parent forms, but this does not mean they are destroyed. In fact, these modified forms can present

different toxicity than their free/parent forms (Rychlik et al., 2014).

3.4. Product “as is”

The current EU regulation –2024/1022 (European Commission, 2024)– states that DON levels cannot exceed 1000 µg/kg in milling products of maize not intended for the final consumer and 400 µg/kg in bakery wares. However, this study was performed according to the past DON legal limits -EU 2023/915 (European Commission, 2023)-, where the limits were 1250 µg/kg for maize flour not intended for the final consumer and 500 µg/kg for bread. On the other hand, FBs are still regulated by EU 2023/915, where they cannot exceed 2000 µg/kg in milled maize not intended for the final consumer and 1000 µg/kg for maize-based products for final consumers. In the previous sections results were given in dry matter basis to make them comparable. However, to study the impact of breadmaking on the real product, toxin levels were calculated in “as is” basis, considering the moisture content, as set by the EU legislation (Scudamore et al., 2009).

Both toxins experienced a reduction in their levels due to the dilution effect of the recipe ingredients (Supplementary Table 1). The actual concentrations in the dough showed decreases of 63.27 ± 4.50 % for DON and 54.22 ± 3.17 % for FBs. After fermentation DON release increased with time, while regarding FBs no change was observed. Baking resulted in an average moisture loss of 30 %, leading to an increase in the concentration of the mycotoxins present. In DON this concentration effect is clearly reflected. For FBs, this effect was hidden by the thermal reduction (Supplementary Table 1).

In the case of DON, as seen in the present experiment, there is a general toxin reduction at the end of the breadmaking process. Even in the condition with higher DON increase (CSD fermented 12 h with high-contaminated flour), this toxin still decreases in bread “as is” by 49.5 % compared to the initial flour (from 1200 to 605.9 µg/kg). However, these reductions are not enough to lower the DON levels under either the previous (500 µg/kg) or the current legal limit (400 µg/kg).

Regarding FBs, in all cases the final concentrations were below the legal limit currently established, suggesting a less concerning situation.

In our case the mycotoxin source (maize flour) only represented 23.8 % of the mass leading to a high dilution effect, but in other cases where the mycotoxin source represents a higher percentage of the recipe, this effect would be reduced, as observed by Scudamore et al. (2009) and Vidal et al. (2014b) as their flours represented around 50 to 60 % of the total mass.

4. Conclusion

Sourdough composition is a critical point during bread making. While literature describes how beneficial LAB are for organoleptic improvements, this study shows that some LAB species of sourdoughs can create new hazards for consumers. Therefore, it is crucial to select and test the strains that will compose the sourdough, as under certain fermentation conditions, some may cleave matrix-bound DON via enzymatic processes. In our study, commercial sourdough ended up increasing the initial DON levels by 30 %, making the product more dangerous than at the beginning. FBs levels were not affected by any fermentation condition. The subsequent heat treatment showed wide decreasing effect in mycotoxin levels (6 to 25 % for DON and 14 to 52 % for FBs) but was not enough to counterbalance the increased DON level in bread prepared with commercial sourdough, leaving it 16 % above the initial concentration. Breadmaking process may not be sufficient to reduce DON levels from a borderline contaminated flour to levels below legal limits in bread. By contrast, the margin given in the regulation for FBs makes it possible to reach safe levels in the product.

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Table 3

Fate of fumonisins B₁ and B₂ during bread baking at 200 °C for 40 min.

Sample Condition		FB ₁	FB ₂
Sourdough type	Initial fumonisin concentration	Variation (% ± SD)	Variation (% ± SD)
WSD	Low	2.08 ± 15.09 ^A	-29.56 ± 19.61 ^Y
	High	-37.93 ± 9.83 ^B	-35.48 ± 12.24 ^{YZ}
ASD	Low	-12.96 ± 7.22 ^A	-53.82 ± 5.09 ^Z
	High	-42.12 ± 5.50 ^B	-31.09 ± 11.95 ^Y
CSD	Low	-8.18 ± 9.79 ^A	-37.53 ± 3.12 ^{YZ}
	High	-48.44 ± 7.83 ^{BC}	-27.12 ± 13.64 ^Y

SD: Standard Deviation. WSD: Without Sourdough; ASD: Artisan Sourdough; CSD: Commercial Sourdough. Within each column, different letters mean that there were significant differences among the means ($p < 0.05$) according to Tukey test.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Alexandre Vicens-Sans: Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Sonia Marín:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Vicente Sanchis:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Antonio J. Ramos:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Francisco Molino:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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